

Polymetallic complexes. Part-CVII : Synthesis, spectral, XRD, molecular modeling and antibacterial study of tetrameric Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes with OON-NOO donor hexadentate azodye ligand

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Abstract : Six tetrameric complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with one new symmetrical OON-NOO donor hexadentate azodye ligand, 4,4'-bis(2'-hydroxy-3'-formyl-5'-nitrophenylazo)diphenylmethane have been synthesized. The characterization of these complexes has been made by elemental analysis, conductance measurement, magnetic, IR, electronic spectra, ESR, NMR, XRD (powdered pattern) and molecular modeling methods. The antibacterial study of the ligand and some of the complexes has been made against Gram-positive bacteria *S. aureus* and Gram-negative bacteria *E. coli*. The Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are found to be distorted octahedral and a tetrahedral stereochemistry has been assigned to Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes. A monoclinic crystal system is suggested for Cu^{II} complex. Crystallite size of the complex was found to be 0.512 nm.

Keywords : Polymetallic complexes, molecular modeling, azodyes.

Introduction

The azodyes are pharmacologically active. In addition to their chemotherapeutic properties¹, they are used as indicators in chemical laboratories and as preservatives and dyeing agents² in industries. Keeping the importance of azodyes, we have been preparing³ a number of multidentate azodye ligands containing oxygen, nitrogen and sulphur donor atoms and their transitional and non-transitional metal complexes. The present study reports the preparation and characterization of hexadentate ligands 4,4'-bis{2'-hydroxy-3'-formyl-5'-bromophenylazo)diphenylmethane and its tetrameric complexes with a aim to study their structural as well as biological activities. An attempt has been made to utilise molecular modeling methods to study the physicochemical properties, electronic and geometrical properties of both the ligand and the complexes along with the mode of bonding of ligand with the metal ions.

Results and discussion

The metal complexes (Table 1) have the general for-

mula [M₄LCl₆(H₂O)₁₀] where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and [M'₄LCl₆(H₂O)₂] where M' = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}. LH₂ = C₂₇H₁₈N₆O₈ (Found : C, 58.25; H, 3.11; N, 15.03. Calcd. C, 58.48; H, 3.24; N, 15.16%), 4,4'-bis(2'-hydroxy-3'-formyl-5'-nitro-phenylazo)diphenylmethane. All the complexes are amorphous in nature, have high melting points and are insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide. Non-electrolytic nature of the complexes is indicated from low conductance values (4.5–5.8 Ω cm² mol⁻¹) in 10⁻³ M solution in DMF⁴.

IR spectra :

In the IR spectra of the ligand, broad-band are observed at 3423 cm⁻¹ which may be attributed to intermolecular O–H...N hydrogen bonding. The absence of this band in the spectra of the metal complexes indicates deprotonation of the phenolic -OH group and bonding of phenolic oxygen to the metal ion⁵. This is further supported by the shift of the band at 1494 cm⁻¹ (LH₂) to ~1470 cm⁻¹ in the metal complexes. The band at 1601

Table 1. Analytical data of the ligand and the complexes

Compd.	M.p. (°C)	Colour	Found (Calcd.) %				
			C	Cl	H	N	M
LH ₂	80	Red	58.25 (58.48)	–	3.04 (3.24)	10.8 (10.10)	–
[Co ₄ LCl ₆ (H ₂ O) ₁₀]	> 240	Coffee	27.24 (27.44)	18.01 (18.03)	1.31 (1.35)	7.08 (7.11)	19.56 (19.96)
[Ni ₄ LCl ₆ (H ₂ O) ₁₀]	> 240	Red	27.16 (27.46)	18.01 (18.05)	1.32 (1.35)	7.08 (7.12)	19.55 (19.89)
[Cu ₄ LCl ₆ (H ₂ O) ₁₀]	> 240	Brown	26.98 (27.02)	17.45 (17.76)	1.3 (1.33)	6.9 (7.0)	21.06 (21.18)
[Zn ₄ LCl ₆ (H ₂ O) ₂]	> 240	Light red	30.15 (30.49)	20.01 (20.04)	0.98 (1.50)	7.6 (7.9)	24.4 (24.61)
[Cd ₄ LCl ₆ (H ₂ O) ₂]	> 240	Brown	25.68 (25.90)	17.01 (17.03)	0.97 (1.27)	6.45 (6.71)	35.76 (35.95)
[Hg ₄ LCl ₆ (H ₂ O) ₂]	> 240	Red	20.15 (20.20)	13.13 (13.28)	0.96 (0.99)	5.19 (5.23)	49.85 (50.04)

cm⁻¹ in the ligand can be attributed to ν(N=N) vibration and in the metal chelates these bands are shown at ~1590 cm⁻¹ which indicates the coordination of one the azo nitrogen atoms to the metal ions⁶. In the ligand a sharp band appears at 1659 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to carbonyl ν(C=O) vibration and in the metal complexes it appears at ~1622–1627 cm⁻¹ indicating the coordination of carbonyl oxygen atom to the metal ions. In the metal complexes broad band appears at 3318–3351 cm⁻¹ followed by sharp peaks at 825–838 cm⁻¹ and at 738–743 cm⁻¹ assignable to OH stretching, rocking and wagging vibrations respectively indicating the presence of coordi-

nated water molecules in the complexes⁷. The conclusive evidence of bonding of the ligand to the metal ions is proved by the appearance of bands at ~506–519 cm⁻¹ (M-O) and at ~474 cm⁻¹ (M-N)⁸.

Electronic absorption spectra and magnetic measurement :

In the electronic spectrum (Table 2) of Ni^{II} complex, four ligand field bands are observed at 10235, 17365, 24990 and 32650 cm⁻¹ respectively assignable to ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{2g}(F) (ν₁), → ³T_{1g}(F) (ν₂), → ³T_{1g}(P) (ν₃) and CT transitions respectively in a distorted-octahedral geometry.

Table 2. Electronic absorption and magnetic measurement data of the complexes

Compd.	μ _{eff} (BM)	ν (cm ⁻¹)	Band assignment	Geometry
[Co ₄ LCl ₆ (H ₂ O) ₁₀]	2.6	8270	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{2g} (F)	Octahedral
		16690	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ A _{2g} (F)	
		20340	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{2g} (P)	
		31450	INCT ^a	
[Ni ₄ LCl ₆ (H ₂ O) ₁₀]	2.2	10240	³ A _{2g} (F) → ³ T _{2g} (F)	Octahedral
		17360	³ A _{2g} (F) → ³ T _{2g} (F)	
		24990	³ A _{2g} (F) → ³ T _{2g} (P)	
		32460	INCT ^a	
[Cu ₄ LCl ₆ (H ₂ O) ₁₀]	1.4	13350	² E _g → ² T _{2g}	Distorted octahedral

^aIntraligand charge transfer spectra.

The ligand field parameters like $Dq = 1024 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 775.3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta_{35} = 0.744 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu_2/\nu_1 = 1.649$ and $\sigma = 34.44$ indicate the distorted octahedral configuration for the complex⁹. The electronic spectrum of Co^{II} complex four bands appear at 82265, 16695, 20340 and 32445 cm^{-1} . The first three bands can be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), $\rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2), $\rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) transitions respectively and the fourth band is assigned to a CT band. The ligand field parameters like $Dq = 842 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 814.6 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta_{35} = 0.836 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu_2/\nu_1 = 2.05$ and $\sigma = 19.33$ suggest a distorted-octahedral geometry for the complex¹⁰. The electronic spectrum of Cu^{II} complex exhibits one broad band at $\sim 13330\text{--}14470 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with maxima at $\sim 14362 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition in support of a distorted-octahedral configuration for the complex¹¹. The sub-normal magnetic moment of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes could be attributed to metal-metal interaction due to super-exchange phenomenon¹² of the phenolic oxygen atoms in a dimeric structure (M-O-M).

ESR spectra :

The ESR spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex has been recorded at X-band at RT. The g_1 , g_2 and g_3 values are found to be 2.02375, 2.08540 and 2.29032 respectively by applying Kneubuhl's method¹³. The axial symmetric parameter (G) is calculated to be 5.3 which indicates strong interaction among magnetically equivalent Cu^{II} ions in the unit cell. In order to obtain information about ground state, another useful parameter (R) is calculated and found to be less than 1 (0.147) which indicates that the ground state is predominantly $d_{x^2-y^2}$. The spin-orbit coupling constant (λ) can be determined by using the equation,

$$g_{av} = 2(1 - 2\lambda/10Dq)$$

where λ = spin-orbit coupling constant.

The value of λ for the Cu^{II} complex is found to be -477.895 cm^{-1} . This lowering of λ value of the complex from the free ion value (-830 cm^{-1}) indicates overlapping of metal-ligand orbitals.

NMR spectra :

The ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectrum of the ligand LH_2 was recorded in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$. The complex pattern observed at δ 7.028–7.733 ppm corresponds to aromatic protons. The sharp peak obtained at δ 10.0693 ppm and at δ 11.385 ppm indicates to phenolic proton and aldehydic proton respectively¹⁴. The spectrum of Zn^{II} complex with the

ligand LH_2 shows no peak at δ 10.0693 ppm indicating deprotonation of phenolic -OH and bonding of oxygen atom with the metal ions.

XRD (powder pattern) study :

The XRD study (powder pattern) of the complex $[\text{Cu}_4\text{LCl}_6(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{10}]$ was made with the help of X-ray diffractometer. The prominent peaks of the diffraction pattern have been indexed and analyzed by the computer programme LSUCRPC¹⁵. The lattice parameters (a , b , c , α , β , γ) and volume of the unit cell have been mentioned along with Miller indices (h,k,l) in the Table 3. The indexing is confirmed by comparing between observed and calculated 2θ values which is evident from the

Table 3. XRD data of the Cu^{II} complex

Observed (2 θ)	Calculated (2 θ)	D spacing	h	k	l	Difference
10.41	10.42	8.481	0	0	1	0.01
10.43	10.43	8.474	1	1	0	0.00
11.95	11.97	7.384	1	1	1	0.02
12.96	12.97	6.820	1	1	-1	0.01
13.95	13.98	6.328	1	2	0	0.03
16.67	16.69	5.309	-1	2	1	0.02
18.31	18.33	4.835	0	3	-1	0.01
26.41	26.42	3.370	3	0	0	0.01
27.48	27.49	3.247	3	0	-1	0.01
30.01	30.01	2.975	-3	3	0	0.00
32.50	32.52	2.751	0	1	3	0.02
33.54	33.56	2.668	2	4	-2	0.02
38.10	38.12	2.359	4	0	1	0.02
41.10	41.13	2.193	-3	2	3	0.03
45.01	45.02	2.012	-2	5	-3	0.01
46.50	46.50	1.951	3	5	2	0.00
50.22	50.24	1.815	4	4	2	0.02
53.04	53.05	1.725	5	0	-3	0.01
56.11	56.12	1.638	-2	1	5	0.01

$$a = 11.022 \text{ \AA}, \alpha = 91.615^\circ, \text{Volume} = 1812.47 \text{ \AA}^3$$

$$b = 9.105 \text{ \AA}, \beta = 95.505^\circ, \text{Density} = 3.16 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$$

$$c = 11.710 \text{ \AA}, \gamma = 89.845^\circ, n = 2.5 \text{ Bravais lattice-c}$$

Figure of Merit-8, Particle size-0.512 nm, Crystal system-Triclinic.

figure of merit (6.4) as suggested by De Wolff¹⁶. The observed and calculated 2θ values of the complex are in good agreement. The density of the complex was determined by the floatation method in a saturated solution of KBr, NaCl and benzene separately. The number of formula units per unit cell (n) is calculated from the relation.

$$n = dNV/M$$

where d = density of the compound, N = Avogadro's number, V = volume of the unit cell, M = molecular weight of the complex. The value of " n " is found to be 1 and which agrees well with the suggested structure of the complex. The crystal system of the complex is found to be monoclinic.

The mean crystallite size of the complex was calculated from the diffraction line width using the Debye-Scherrer relation,

$$B = K\lambda/\beta \cos \theta$$

where B = particle size, K = dimensionless shape factor, λ = X-ray wave length, β = line broadening at half the maximum intensity, θ = diffraction angle. This equation relates the size of the particles in a solid with the broadening of a peak in a diffraction pattern. The crystallite size of the complex was found to be 0.512 nm.

Molecular modeling study :

Molecular modeling of the ligand and the complex has been carried out using molecular mechanics and Hartree-Fock (HF) quantum mechanics. The standard 6-31G basis set was used in conjugation with H-F method. All calculations are made using Gaussian 98 programme. The ligand LH₂ (Fig. 3) and its Co^{II} complex (Fig. 4) are built and their geometries are optimized at MM/H-F/6-31G level of theory.

The results of the structural calculations have been used to compute the quantitative structure activity relationships properties. The molecular parameter of the ligand are; total energy (-0.28526 kcal/mol), heat of formation (-476.82 kcal/mol), repulsion energy (48283 eV), electronic energy (-55763.1 eV), HOMO (-8.57906 eV) and LUMO (1.33226 eV). The QSAR properties of the ligand are; volume 47210.56 Å³, surface area 126.94 Å², log p 5.004, refractivity 15.2462 Å³/mol, β polarisability -68.5556 and α polarisability 164.1366.

In the metal complex, the metal may be coordinated to either N(1) or N(2) of the azo group. When it is coordinated to N(1), it forms a six membered ring and it forms a five membered ring when coordinated to (N2). In case of Co^{II} complex with LH₂ the total energy is 190 kcal/mol and 211.63 kcal/mol, when it forms the five member and six member ring respectively which suggests that the Co^{II} ion is coordinated to N(2) of the azo

Fig. 1

X = H₂O for M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and M = O for M = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

group forming a five membered ring. Since the energy of the five membered ring is lower, the metal ion is bonded to the N(2) of the azo group forming a five membered ring (Table 4).

Antibacterial study :

The ligand and its complexes (Table 5) were screened against Gram-positive bacteria *S. aureus* and Gram-nega-

Table 4. Selected bond length and bond angles of ligand and complex

Compd.	Bond	Bond	
		length (Å)	angle (°)
Ligand-LH ₂	O(14)-H(44)	1.033	C(5)-C(6)-C(3)-120
	C(2)-N(8)	1.434	C(6)-C(7)-H(84)-120
	C(23)-O(28)	1.407	O(82)-N(81)-O(83)-106.7
	C(5)-C(6)	1.379	C(23)-C(22)-N(15)-120
	N(8)-N(9)	1.270	
[Co ₄ LCl ₆ (H ₂ O) ₁₀]	O(13)-Co(11)	1.964	N(9)-Co(11)-O(10)-90
	N(9)-Co(11)	1.972	N(9)-Co(11)-Cl(12)-90
	Cl(12)-Co(11)	2.359	O(10)-Co(11)-Cl(12)-90
	N(78)-O(79)	1.362	O(10)-Co(11)-O(13)-90

Table 5. Antibacterial screening of the ligands and complexes

Compd.	Concentration (µg ml ⁻¹)	Zone of inhibition (mm)	
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
LH ₂	500	10	9
[Co ₄ LCl ₆ (H ₂ O) ₁₀]	500	12	10
[Ni ₄ LCl ₆ (H ₂ O) ₁₀]	500	13	12
[Cu ₄ LCl ₆ (H ₂ O) ₁₀]	500	14	12
[Zn ₄ LCl ₆ (H ₂ O) ₂]	500	10	8
Tetracycline	1000	45	30

tive bacteria *E. coli*. The ligand and complexes were found to have antibacterial properties. The Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes have more antibacterial activities than the ligand while the Zn^{II} complex possess same activity and it can be explained on the basis of chelation theory²¹.

Fig. 5. Potential surface of the ligand.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AR grade (Merck or BDH). Elemental analysis (C, H, N) were carried out on elemental analyser Perkin-Elmer 2400 while metals were estimated by EDTA titration method after decomposing the complexes with concentrated HNO₃. The chlorine con-

tents were estimated by a standard method. The molar conductance measurements of the complexes were made using Toshniwal CL-06 conductivity bridge in 10⁻³ M solution in DMF. The magnetic susceptibility measurements of the complexes were made on a Guoy balance at room temperature, using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as calibrant. Electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded (10⁻³ M in DMF) using Hilger-Watt Uvispeck spectrophotometer, ESR of the Cu^{II} complex was recorded in an E4-spectrometer, NMR on a Jeol GSX 400 with DMSO as solvent and TMS as internal standard. The X-ray diffraction (Powder pattern) of the complex was recorded on a Phillips PW 1130 diffractometer with scan axis-Gonio, start position (2θ - 10.004), end position (2θ - 79.9764), anode material - Cu, K - ALPHA1 (Å) 1.54060 and generator setting - 30 mA, 40 KV, and molecular modelling of the ligand and complex was done with the help of Arguslab 4.01 software.

The antibacterial study of the ligand and the complexes has been made using cup-plate method²¹. The compounds were tested at the concentration of 500 µg/ml in DMSO. A 0.2 ml of each was placed in a well made in the nutrient agar medium in which culture of the tested bacteria has been spread to produce uniform growth. The diameter of inhibition zone in mm was measured after 24 h of incubation at 37 °C after comparing with the standard drug tetracycline.

Preparation of the ligand :

The azodye was prepared by coupling reaction of a diazonium chloride obtained from 4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane (0.01 mol, 1.98 g) with alkaline solution of 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde (0.02 mol, 3.06 g) at 0-5 °C (Fig. 1).

Preparation of the complexes :

The metal chlorides in ethanol were mixed separately with ethanolic solution of the ligand LH₂ in 4 : 1 molar ratio. The resulting solution were heated to 50-60 °C for about 1 h on a heating mantle and the pH was raised to ~7 by adding conc. NH₄OH drop by drop with stirring. The solid metal complexes thus formed were then washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum (Fig. 2).

Conclusion

The Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes possess distorted-

octahedral geometry and a tetrahedral geometry is suggested for Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II} complexes. It is found that the azodye behaves as dibasic hexadentate ligand coordinating through phenolic oxygen, azo nitrogen and carbonyl oxygen atoms. The ligand forms tetrameric complexes with the metal ions. The XRD study suggests monoclinic crystal system for [Cu₄LCl₆(H₂O)₁₀]. All the calculations based on the molecular mechanics on the optimized geometries fit well with the experimental findings. Both the ligand and their complexes possess antibacterial activities against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria.

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